

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

Physics-Informed and Explainable AI for Wind Turbine Condition Monitoring and Structural Health Monitoring (PhIE-WinTurCoM)

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Project modality	Coordinated project (oriented research). Thematic priorities: Energy and mobility; Digitalisation and telecommunications.
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Coordinating subproject (SP1)	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) — CoDALab / WinTurCoM, Escola d'Enginyeria de Barcelona Est (EEBE). PIs: Yolanda Vidal; Francesc Pozo.
Subproject 2 (SP2)	IKERLAN. PIs: Óscar Salgado; Mireia Olave.
DMP responsible / data steward	Yolanda Vidal (Coordinator, WP0). ORCID: 0000-0003-4964-6948.
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This plan follows the Science Europe core requirements and the Horizon Europe DMP structure, and complies with the open-science obligations of Law 17/2022 amending the Spanish Law on Science, Technology and Innovation, the AEI open-access and FAIR-data requirements, and the FAIR principles. It is aligned with the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA).

1. Data summary

PhIE-WinTurCoM develops physics-informed and explainable artificial-intelligence methods for condition monitoring (CM) and structural health monitoring (SHM) of onshore and offshore wind turbines. Its purpose in relation to data is twofold: to reuse real operational data made available by industrial partners under confidentiality agreements, and to generate new, openly shareable synthetic, experimental and derived datasets that address the scarcity of fault-labelled data in the wind-energy sector. Data are collected, generated and processed to develop and validate the project's four scientific pillars (multirate SCADA/CMS fusion, inverse physics-informed inference, explainable diagnosis, and population-based fleet-wide health indexing).

The project handles four main data categories, organised by work package (WP). Their type, origin, format, estimated volume and intended openness are summarised below.

Dataset (WP)	Type and content	Formats	Est. size	Openness
WP1 — Observational industrial data (SCADA + CMS)	Real operational wind-turbine data: 10-minute SCADA variables (temperature, power, wind speed, pitch) paired with high-frequency (kHz) gearbox/generator vibration; healthy and faulty periods.	.csv, .parquet, .mat, proprietary CMS formats	Several TB	Restricted — third-party data under NDA. Not shared; only anonymised, non-identifying derivatives may be disseminated.

Dataset (WP)	Type and content	Formats	Est. size	Openness
WP2 — Synthetic simulation data	High-fidelity synthetic vibration and operational signals with ground-truth physical parameters and seeded failure modes, generated with OpenFAST/SubDyn and physics-based models.	.csv, .npy, .mat	Hundreds of GB	Open — deposited in CORA-RDR with DOI and metadata.
WP3 — Experimental test-rig data	Drivetrain test-bench measurements (high-frequency vibration, torque, speed, load, temperature) with labelled mechanical faults under non-stationary loading; generated at the CoDAlab drivetrain rig (EEBE-UPC).	.csv, .tdms, .mat + documentation	1–3 TB	Open — deposited in CORA-RDR with DOI, metadata and ground-truth fault labels.
WP4 — Fleet-level derived data	Graph-structured wind-farm representations, standardised anomaly scores, health indicators and global health index (GHI) values, derived from WP1–WP3.	.csv, .parquet, .npy, .mat, model files	Up to tens of GB	Mixed — confidential when derived from NDA-protected WP1 data; only anonymised or fully synthetic outputs are shared.

The WP1 operational data are provided by a leading offshore wind energy developer and operator (hereafter “the industrial data provider”) under a non-disclosure agreement. So that this DMP can be published openly, the partner’s identity is withheld here; it is recorded in the confidential project documentation.

In addition, long-term structural monitoring data from the Alpha Ventus offshore wind farm are reused in WP2.2 (SHM) under a formal agreement within the RAVE (Research at Alpha Ventus) initiative; these are restricted-access third-party data. Publicly available benchmark datasets (e.g., CWRU bearing data) are used only for preliminary calibration and are not re-distributed. No personal data are collected, generated or processed at any stage of the project.

Data utility: the open synthetic and experimental datasets (WP2, WP3) and the anonymised derived indicators (WP4) are expected to be of high value to the wind-energy, structural-dynamics, prognostics-and-health-management and machine-learning communities, addressing the well-documented lack of fault-labelled, openly available wind-turbine data. The group has an established track record of releasing reusable datasets, including a bolt-loosening SHM dataset (Data in Brief, 2024; CORA) that has exceeded 922,000 downloads, and a rotor-imbalance dataset (2025).

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable

- Open datasets are deposited in CORA – Repositori de Dades de Recerca (CORA-RDR, operated by CSUC) and/or Zenodo, both of which issue a persistent Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and expose DataCite-compliant metadata.
- Each dataset is described with rich metadata: title, authors with ORCID identifiers, institution, funder and grant reference, keywords, version, spatial/temporal coverage where relevant, related publications, and links to associated software.

- Datasets are accompanied by a README/codebook documenting variables, units, sampling rates, file structure and provenance, to ensure they are discoverable and understandable independently of the publications.
- A consistent file-naming convention and explicit semantic versioning are applied; each released version receives its own DOI, with version DOIs grouped under a concept DOI.
- Datasets and their related articles are cross-linked through DOIs; publications cite the data DOIs and vice versa.

2.2 Making data openly accessible

The project applies the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. Synthetic (WP2), experimental (WP3) and anonymised derived (WP4) datasets are made openly available by default, with no embargo beyond the time required for quality control and publication. They are deposited in CORA-RDR/Zenodo, which provide open, standards-based access (HTTP, OAI-PMH harvesting) without registration.

- Restricted data (the WP1 SCADA/CMS data from the industrial data provider; Alpha Ventus/RAVE structural data) cannot be shared due to binding non-disclosure and data-use agreements. Where scientifically essential, access may be requested from the data owners; the project will only release derivatives that are anonymised and stripped of any turbine- or wind-farm-identifying information.
- Software and code underpinning the results are released openly (see Section 3), enabling validation and reuse of the methods even where the underlying industrial data are restricted.
- Peer-reviewed publications are made open access in compliance with the AEI and EU mandates, through UPC transformative agreements (Wiley, Elsevier, Springer, AIP, IEEE), gold open access where supported, or green deposit of the accepted manuscript in CORA/UPCommons. Diamond open-access venues with open peer review (e.g., Wind Energy Science) are prioritised where appropriate.

2.3 Making data interoperable

- Open, non-proprietary or widely supported formats are used for archiving (.csv, .parquet, .npy, plus documented .mat and .tdms), ensuring long-term readability and tool independence.
- DataCite metadata schema is used for dataset description; controlled vocabularies and domain conventions (e.g., standard SCADA signal taxonomies, modal-analysis parameters, IEA Wind data conventions) are followed where applicable to maximise interoperability with sector datasets.
- Physics-based models and synthetic data are generated with community-standard tools (OpenFAST/SubDyn), and configuration files are released alongside the data to allow regeneration and integration.

2.4 Increasing data re-use

- Open datasets are released under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence (CC BY 4.0); accompanying documentation is released under CC BY 4.0. (Licence choice to be confirmed by the consortium.)
- Source code and software are released under a permissive OSI-approved licence (e.g., MIT or Apache-2.0) to maximise reuse; the exact licence will be agreed by the consortium and stated in each repository.

- Data quality is ensured through documented preprocessing, validation against ground truth (for synthetic and experimental data), and provenance records; experimental datasets include precise fault labels.
- Released data remain reusable for at least the period required by the funder and the host institutions (a minimum of five years after project end), guaranteed by the long-term preservation services of CORA-RDR/Zenodo.
- Restricted industrial data are retained according to the terms of the corresponding NDAs and institutional governance policies.

3. Other research outputs (software and code)

Beyond datasets, the project produces software as a primary research output: data-fusion modules, inverse physics-informed and explainability code, finite-element modelling tools (OpenFAST/SubDyn), surrogate models, graph-neural-network code, and deployment containers (Docker).

- Code is developed in public version-controlled repositories (GitHub) and, for citable, preserved releases, archived in Zenodo to obtain a persistent DOI, ensuring it is findable, citable and FAIR (GitHub alone does not guarantee persistence).
- Each released repository includes an open licence, a README with installation and usage instructions, dependency specifications and, where feasible, example data and reproducible environments.
- Software released by the project credits all contributors (including PhD researchers) with appropriate authorship and ORCID identifiers.

4. Allocation of resources

- Open-access publication fees (APCs) and the costs associated with FAIR data sharing are foreseen in the project budget; deposit in CORA-RDR and Zenodo is free of charge.
- The Coordinator (Y. Vidal, WP0) acts as data steward and is responsible for the implementation, monitoring and updating of this DMP; each WP leader is responsible for documenting and depositing the datasets generated within their WP, supported by the UPC Library and Research Support Service and the CSUC CORA service.
- Data-management effort (curation, metadata creation, deposit) is integrated into the tasks of the work team and the doctoral training plan, which includes UPC ICE training on open science and FAIR data.
- Long-term preservation is provided by CORA-RDR and Zenodo; no additional preservation infrastructure costs are anticipated.

5. Data security

During the project, all data are stored on UPC/CoDAlab and IKERLAN institutional servers with encryption, role-based access control and regular backups, in accordance with the host institutions' ICT security policies.

- NDA-restricted data (the WP1 data from the industrial data provider; Alpha Ventus/RAVE) are kept in access-restricted directories accessible only to authorised researchers, physically and logically separated from openly shareable data.
- Backups and recovery procedures follow institutional governance; high-performance computing and storage resources (CoDAlab servers and the requested GPU server,

IKERLAN DIGILAB-AI and distributed-computing infrastructure) are managed under controlled-access policies.

- For long-term retention, only non-confidential datasets are transferred to the trusted repositories (CORA-RDR/Zenodo), which provide secure, certified preservation and integrity checks.

6. Ethical aspects

The project does not collect, generate or process personal data: all datasets relate exclusively to mechanical, operational and vibration signals from turbines or laboratory rigs, and to derived engineering indicators. No ethics approval for human-subjects data is therefore required.

- WP1 data are subject to confidentiality under non-disclosure agreements with the industrial data provider (signed 12/12/2023 and 09/10/2025); access to raw data is limited to authorised researchers, and any disseminated derivative is anonymised and stripped of turbine- and wind-farm-identifying information.
- Alpha Ventus structural data are reused under a formal agreement with the Federal Republic of Germany within the RAVE initiative (signed 16/08/2023) and are treated as restricted third-party data.
- WP2 (synthetic) and WP3 (experimental) data carry no ethical restrictions. WP4 outputs are treated as confidential when derived from NDA-protected data; only anonymised or fully synthetic outputs are shared publicly.
- A gender perspective is applied to data handling and dissemination, including inclusive communication and attention to indirect biases, in line with the project's equality commitments.

7. Other issues (policies and standards)

- This DMP complies with the open-science obligations introduced by Law 17/2022 (amending Spain's Law 14/2011 on Science, Technology and Innovation), which mandate open access to publications and FAIR management of research data funded with public resources, and with the corresponding AEI requirements under the PEICTI 2024–2027.
- As an EU co-funded action, the project also aligns with the European open-science framework and the FAIR principles.
- Institutional policies of UPC (UPCommons, CORA) and the host institutions on research-data management and open access are followed.
- This is a living document: it will be reviewed and updated at least at the project mid-term and at project completion, and whenever significant changes occur in the data being generated or in the applicable agreements. Updated versions will be redeposited with new version DOIs.

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